

VARIATION IN SHAPE DISTORTION DUE TO CORNER THINNING/THICKENING OF PREPREG

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SUMMARY

Shape distortion and thickness of composite corners during traditional prepreg manufacturing has been investigated. Components have been manufactured on a tool with both male and female corners using prepreg with both “unsolved toughener” and “solved toughener”. In addition, two cure assemblies have been used to alter the corner effects.

Keywords: Shape distortion, Corner thinning, Prepreg, Cure assembly, Experiments

INTRODUCTION

For channel and angle components as shown in Figure 1, the distortion in shape will be visible by a change in angle. The phenomenon is often termed as spring-in and is a result of different expansion in the in-plane and the through-thickness direction of the laminate [1]. The corner radius [2] do not affect the spring-in angle if the laminate is homogeneous orthotropic through the thickness. However, when a corner is produced by autoclave where only one half of the tool is stiff, local corner thinning/thickening during processing [1] is expected. During traditional prepreg manufacturing it is well known that corner thickening might occur at female tool corners and corner thinning might occur at male corners [3, 4]. A change in thickness means a change in fibre volume fraction which affects spring-in. Radford and Rennick [1] observed that the larger corner radius, the less corner effects.

Shape distortion and thicknesses of composite corners during traditional prepreg manufacturing have been investigated as a factorial design in this study.

Figure 1. Illustration of tool and component.

MANUFACTURING EXPERIMENTS

Seven components manufactured by traditional autoclave curing, illustrated in Figure 1 and described in Table 1 have been manufactured to investigate the effect on thickness and spring-in. Spring-in, $\Delta\theta$ is the change of external angle θ of a symmetric and balanced lay-up, illustrated on the right in Figure 1. Two different materials, two cure assemblies and female and male tool corners have been used to alter the corner effects.

The tool was made from carbon fibre composite with a male and female radius of R8 and R6, respectively. This means that components manufactured on a male corner will have an inner and outer radius of 8 and 12 mm, respectively. A component manufactured on a female radius will have an inner and outer radius of 2 and 6 mm.

The 977-2 and the M21 prepreg system was cured on the left and right side in Figure 2, respectively. On each side, three reference points on the web were used as reference system. The reference points were transferred to each component during cure.

Figure 2. Tool and components after demoulding.

Material

The materials used in the study were Hexply M21/T700 (268g/m²) and Cycom 977-2/HTS (134g/m²), these are UD prepreg systems with “unsolved toughener” and “solved toughener”, respectively. The lay-up were [0/45/90/-45]_{2s} and [0₂/45₂/90₂/-45₂]_{2s} for the M21 and 977-2, respectively, The nominal thickness was 4.2 mm for both. All composnets were cured in an autoclave with with an identical cure cycle: 7bar, heating (1.5°C/min) to 180°C and hold for 2h followed by cooling (3°C/min).

Cure assembly

Two different cure assemblies have been used in order to change the corner effects. The first is a standard cure assembly (Std) expected to result in large corner effects. The second type is an improved cure assembly (Improved) where the tension in the vacuum bag is minimised by folds and a slow and careful application of the vacuum during debulking and curing.

Table 1. Manufactured components.

Component	Assembly	Material
1	Standard	977-2
2	Standard	M21
3	Standard	977-2
4	Standard	M21
5	Improved	M21
6	Improved	977-2
7	Improved	M21

Figure 3. Definition of tool positions

MEASUREMENTS

The thicknesses of each component were measured along a cross section in the middle a calliper at nine positions, identified as A to I in Figure 3.

The angle measurements were performed by Svensk Verktygsteknik [4] using an optical coordinate measuring machine (TRITOP from GOM International AG [5]). This is a mobile optical measuring device designed to define the exact 3D position of markers.

From the reference system on the tool and components three cross sections were defined and ten markers were attached at each cross section according to Figure 4. Then the 3D position of the markers on the tool and components were measured. The position of the markers were used to define vectors and the angles between flanges and web at position B, D, F and H were calculated by the measuring software.

Figure 4. Markers attached to a component and calculated angles, B to H in Section 1.

RESULTS

Table 2 contains the thicknesses at each position defined in Figure 3 for the seven manufactured components. In Table 2, the angles between the web and the flanges are presented for the tool and each component. Section and positions are defined in Figure 3 and Figure 4, respectively. Tool 1 and Tool 2 in Table 3 are the location where the M21 and 977-2 components were manufactured. Spring-in is defined as the difference between the angle of the tool and the component in Table 3 and is summarised in Table 4 together with normalised thicknesses.

Table 2. Thickness (mm) of the components at each position, defined in Figure 3.

Position	Components						
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
A	3.7	4.1	3.9	4.2	4.2	4.2	4.2
B	7.2	5.4	6.9	4.8	4.8	5.2	4.6
C	4.3	4.2	4.2	4.2	4.2	4.3	4.2
D	3.4	4.1	3.6	4.2	4.2	4.2	4.2
E	4.3	4.3	4.4	4.2	4.2	4.3	4.2
F	3.5	4.1	3.7	4.2	4.2	4.2	4.2
G	4.3	4.2	4.1	4.2	4.2	4.3	4.2
H	7.1	5.5	6.5	4.8	4.8	5.2	4.7
I	3.6	4.2	4.1	4.2	4.2	4.2	4.2

Table 3. Angles (°) at each position and section, defined in Figure 4.

Position	977-2			M21		
	Section 1	Section 2	Section 3	Section 1	Section 2	Section 3
		Tool 2			Tool 1	
B	99.6	99.6	99.6	99.7	99.7	99.8
D	102.5	102.5	102.7	102.5	102.6	102.8
F	102.4	102.5	102.3	102.7	102.7	102.6
H	99.8	99.8	99.7	99.8	99.8	100.0
		Component 1			Component 2	
B	98.7	98.7	98.5	98.7	98.5	98.5
D	101.4	101.6	101.6	101.1	101.2	101.2
F	101.7	101.6	101.6	101.1	101.0	101.2
H	98.9	98.8	98.8	98.8	98.7	98.8
		Component 3			Component 4	
B	97.9	97.8	97.8	98.5	98.5	98.5
D	102.0	102.2	102.2	101.1	101.3	101.3
F	102.3	102.1	102.2	101.1	101.1	101.2
H	98.4	98.4	98.4	98.8	98.7	98.8
					Component 5	
B				98.6	98.5	98.6
D				101.1	101.3	101.4
F				101.2	101.2	101.2
H				99.0	99.1	99.2
		Component 6			Component 7	
B	98.7	98.7	98.7	98.7	98.6	98.6
D	101.2	101.3	101.4	101.1	101.2	101.3
F	101.5	101.4	101.4	101.1	101.2	101.2
H	99.1	99.0	99.0	99.0	98.9	99.1

Table 4. Normalised thickness (% of nominal thickness) at the corner of a laminate manufactured on a female and male tool corner, respectively.

Material	Normalised thickness (% of nominal)				Spring-in (°)			
	977-2		M21		977-2		M21	
Cure assembly ¹	Std	Imp	Std	Imp	Std	Imp	Std	Imp
Female ²	166%	125%	131%	112%	1.3	0.8	1.2	1.0
Male ²	87%	101%	100%	100%	0.6	1.1	1.5	1.4

1. Std – Standard cure assembly, Imp – Improved cure assembly.
2. Female – Female tool corner, Male – Male tool corner, see Figure 1.

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

The manufacturing of components has been performed as a factorial experiment, which allows us to study the effect of each factor and the interactions between factors on a thickness and spring-in (response variable). The factors are:

- Material (977-2 and M21)
- Assembly (Standard and Improved)
- Position for thickness measurements (A to H in Figure 3)
 - Type (Female (B and H), Male (D and F), Flanges (A, C and G))
- Section and position for spring-in measurement in Figure 4.
 - Corner (Female (B and H) and Male (D and F))

Thickness

All thicknesses in Table 2 were analysed using multifactor ANOVA (“Analysis of Variance”) while considering 2nd order interactions [7] with Material, Position and Assembly as factors. The result showed that all factors and the interactions between Material-Position and Position-Assembly statistically significant effect on Thickness at the 95.0% confidence level.

For 977-2 components the standard cure assembly result in thickening and thinning of female (Position B, H) and male corner (Position D and F), respectively. The improved cure assembly decrease the thickening of the female corner and the male corner showed less thinning, see Figure 5.

For the M21 components, it was only the female corners (Position B and H) that were affected. The improved cure assembly had no effect on the flanges or the male corners but decrease the thickness of the female corners according to left graph in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Thickness at different positions (defined Figure 3) for standard and improved cure assembly, 95% confidence level.

Spring-in

Spring-in calculated from the angles in Table 3 were analysed using multifactor ANOVA (“Analysis of Variance”) while considering 2nd order interactions [7] with Section, Corner, Assembly, Material as factors reveal that Material is the only significant main affects at the 95% confidence level. The analysis also shows that Corner-Assembly and Assembly-Material are significant interactions.

In Figure 6 each material has been analysed separately and the interaction between the cure assembly and the position have been plotted.

Figure 6. Spring-in at different positions (defined in Figure 4) for standard and improved cure assembly, 95% confidence level.

A multifactor ANOVA analysis of the 977-2 components shows no significant main effect at the 95% confidence level. However, the interaction between the Corner and Assembly is significant at the 95% confidence level.

From Figure 6, no interaction effects are expected for the M21 components and an ANOVA analysis proves that both the cure assembly (standard or improved) and the corner (female and male) are significant main effects for the M21 components at the 95% confidence level, see Figure 7.

Figure 7. Significant factors for M21.

CROSS SECTIONS

A piece of each corner was casted into neat resin and polished in order to investigate the corners further, see Figure 8. From the cross sections, the corner thinning/thickening of 977-2 cured with a standard cure assembly is obvious. For a female corner cured with a standard cure assembly, it is clear that the fibre distribution through the thickness is different for 977-2 compared to M21. The micrograph of a female M21 corner cured with a standard cure assembly shows a resin rich area on top of the laminate. For a 977-2 component the same conditions will result in a thicker component with evenly distributed fibres. This means that the volume fraction in the laminate is higher than nominal for M21 and correspondingly, the fibre fraction in a female tool corner is lower in a 977-2 laminate.

Increased thickness at a female tool corner of a 977-2 component results in low fibre fraction, see Figure 8. This indicates larger expansion through the thickness and as a result larger spring-in. This phenomenon can explain the large spring-in in Table 4 for 977-2 cured with the standard cure assembly as well as the correspondingly low spring-in at a male corner, subjected to corner thinning.

The result for M21 in Table 4 shows a lower spring-in at the female corner even if the female corner is thicker. This might be explained by lower expansion trough the

thickness due to the fact that the actual laminate has a higher fibre fraction as well as a resin rich area as shown in Figure 9.

Figure 8. Cross sections from different corners.

Figure 9. Micrograph of a M21 laminate cured on a female corner with a standard cure assembly.

CONCLUSIONS

The material with “unsolved toughener” (M21) shows completely different behaviour than the material with “solved toughener” (977-2). The components manufactured by 977-2 showed much larger experimental scatter than components manufactured from M21.

A M21 prepreg manufactured on a male tool corner is not affected by the cure assembly and a thickness close to the nominal value is expected. On a female tool corner on the other hand corner thickening is likely. The thickening effect at a female tool corner is stronger for 977-2 than for M21.

The grand average spring-in angle is larger for M21 than 977-2, 1.3° compared to 1.0°. According to Table 4 and Figure 5 to 7 the shape distortion behaviour of M21 is different from the behaviour of 977-2.

For M21 both the cure assembly and the tool corner (female/male) affect the spring-in. An improved cure assembly decrease the spring-in and the spring-in is less for a component manufactured on a female tool corner than on a male tool corner.

For 977-2 there is an interaction effect between the corner and the cure assembly. For the traditional cure assembly a female tool corner result in larger spring-in but for the improved cure assembly a male tool corner result in larger spring-in.

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References

1. Radford DW, Rennick TS. Separating Sources of Manufacturing Distortion in Lamianted Composites. *Journal of Plastics and Composites* 2000;19(8):621-641.
2. Holmberg JA. Influence of Chemical Shrinkage on Shape Distortion of RTM Composites. Proc 19th International SAMPE European Conference of the Society for the Advancement of Material and Process Engineering, Paris, France, 22-24 April, 1998. p. 621-632.
3. Fernlund G, Griffith J, Courdjia R, Poursartipa A. Experimental and numerical study of the effect of caul-sheets on corner thinning of composite laminates. *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing* 2002;33:411-426.
4. Wisnom MR, Gigliotti M, Ersoy N, Campbell M, Potter KD. Mechanisms generating residual stresses and distortion during manufacture of polymer-matrix composite structures *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing* 2006;37:522-529.
5. Svensk Verktysteknik AB, Aurorum 6, SE-977 75 Luleå, Sweden, Aurorum 6, SE-977 75 Luleå, Sweden.
6. GOM International AG, Bremgarterstrasse 89B, CH-8967 Widnau, Switzerland.
7. Box GEP, Hunter WG, Hunter JS. *Statistics for experimenters: An introduction to Design, Data analysis and Model building*, John Wiley & Sons Inc, 1978.